

ABU BAKR MUHAMMAD ZAKARIYYA AR-ROZIYNING AQLNING FAZILATI HAQIDAGI QARASHLARI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18296192>

Annotation

This article examines the moral doctrine of the prominent thinker Abu Bakr Muhammad Zakariyya al-Razi. It analyzes his views on the acquisition of moral virtues and the elimination of human flaws, emphasizing reason as the most fundamental, reliable, and effective theoretical basis for regulating human behavior. In al-Razi's ethical teaching, reason is interpreted as the greatest blessing bestowed by God upon humankind, enabling individuals to rise above sensual desires and emotions and to achieve moral and spiritual perfection. The study explores the rationalist and epistemological foundations of al-Razi's thought, particularly the relationship between reason, will, and emotions, as well as the leading role of reason in the process of cognition, perception, and human self-control. The article concludes that, according to al-Razi, constant reliance on reason is the primary means of attaining happiness, moral integrity, and intellectual maturity.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada buyuk mutafakkir Abu Bakr Muhammad Zakariyyo ar-Roziyning axloqiy ta'limoti tahlil qilinadi. Unda mutafakkirning axloqiy fazilatlarni egallash va insoniy nuqsonlarni bartaraf etish masalasiga oid qarashlari yoritilib, aqlning inson xatti-harakatlarini boshqaruvchi asosiy va ishonchli nazariy mezon sifatidagi o'rni ochib beriladi. Ar-Roziy ta'limotida aql Alloh tomonidan insonga berilgan eng ulug' ne'mat sifatida talqin qilinib, u insonni hayvoniy mayl va his-tuyg'ulardan ustun qo'yuvchi, ma'naviy kamolot sari yetaklovchi kuch sifatida baholanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Axloqiy ta'limot, aql, aqlning fazilati, ratsionalizm, axloqiy fazilat, nuqsonlarni bartaraf etish, inson xatti-harakati, aqliy salohiyat, gnoseologiya, bilish jarayoni, sezgi va idrok, his-tuyg'ular, iroda.

Key words: Moral doctrine, reason, the virtue of reason, rationalism, moral virtue, elimination of flaws, human behavior, intellectual potential, epistemology, process of cognition, sensation and perception, emotions, will.

Ar-Roziy axloqiy ta'limoti izchil ratsionalizm tamoyiliga asoslangan. Inson xatti-harakatining, ehtiyojij intilishlarining bosh yo'naltiruvchi omili uning aqliy salohiyatidir [1]. Shu bilan birga ar-Roziy inson afzalliklari va axloqiy xatti-harakatlarining gnoseologik ildizlarini ham ko'rsatadi [3]. Chunki, aql tufayli hatti-harakatlarimizni sezgida paydo bo'lguniga qadar tasavvur qilamiz, huddi "his qilganday ko'ramiz" [4]. Agar aql bo'lmasa, sezgi va hislarimiz qanchalik asosli bo'lmasin, biz "hayvonlar, go'daklar va majnunlar holati"da qolamiz [5].

Ar-Roziy aqlni insonni olijanoblikka etaklovchi, fazilatli qiluvchi ne'mat, kuchli qurol sifatida baholaydi [2]. Shu bilan birga u insonning hirslari, xohish-istaklari va his-tuyg'ulari har doim aql ko'rsatmalariga rioya qilmasligini, aksincha, uni o'ziga bo'ysundirishga harakat

qilishini ta'kidlaydi [6]. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, inson irodasi aqldan ustun bo'lishga intilishi mumkin. Bunday holatning yuz bermasligi uchun inson o'z his-tuyg'ularini aqlga bo'ysundirish, ya'ni o'z "jonini jilovlab olishi" zarur. Faqat shu holda ruh butun musaffoligi bilan jilovlanadi va inson o'z ko'zlagan maqsadiga erishadi.

Ar-Roziy aqlning sezgilardan, his-tuyg'ulardan va insoniy xohish-irodalardan afzal ekanligini ta'kidlagan, biroq irodaning nisbiy erkinligini ham e'tirof etgan [6]. Ammo irodaning bu nisbiyligi aql nazoratidan chiqmasligi kerak; inson o'z irodasiga emas, balki aqlga murojaat qilishi lozim. Shunday qilib, "Biz hamma ishlarimizda unga (aqlga) yuz tutishimiz, hatti-harakatlarimizni u bilan muvofiqlashtirishimiz, ularni amalga oshirishimizda unga suyanishimiz zarur... O'z hirslarimizni majburan unga yuklamasligimiz lozim".

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